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Impact of Fiscal Decentralization on Healthcare Outcomes:

Empirical Evidence from Punjab, Pakistan

Ambreen Sarwar

School of Economics, University of Punjab, Pakistan. Email: ambreen.eco@pu.edu.pk

Atif Khan Jadoon*

School of Economics, University of Punjab, Pakistan. Corresponding Author Email:
atifkhan.eco@pu.edu.pk

Maham Nasir

School of Economics, University of Punjab, Pakistan.

Email: maham.nasr56@gmail.com

Maria Faiq Javaid

School of Economics, University of the Punjab, Pakistan.

Email: mariafaiq.eco@pu.edu.pk

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Abstract

This study examines how fiscal decentralization (FISD) impacts the efficiency of public service delivery (EPSD) in Punjab, Pakistan, from 1989 to 2024. It uses stochastic frontier analysis to estimate changing efficiency and measures how fiscal decentralization influences these results using the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). In the short run, revenue decentralization (RED) improves the efficiency coefficient for infant mortality rate (ECINFM), while expenditure decentralization reduces it significantly. In the long run, both RED and EXD have positive and significant effects on health sector efficiency.

Keywords: Fiscal Decentralization, Efficiency, Health Sector, Stochastic Frontier Analysis

1. Introduction

Decentralization is often considered a panacea for inefficient government performance in public service delivery. Recent economic, fiscal, and financial crises across many nations have made public-sector efficiency the center of debate, and many global policymakers promote fiscal decentralization (FISD) as a useful measure to improve public-sector efficiency (Arends, 2017). FISD is a widely practiced policy that gives greater autonomy to lower tiers of government by allocating pooling and spending responsibilities from the central government to lower levels within a country (Rotulo et al., 2022; Sarwar et al., 2022). Decentralized structures are more reflective and responsive to local needs (Ahmad et al., 2020). Local government can use its power and authority to improve the quality of human capital by providing better social services, such as housing, education, health care, and sanitation (Mehr-un-Nisa & Khalil, 2018; Ali & Senturk, 2019; Sarwar et al., 2022). Since health is a key determinant of individuals' quality of life (Martinez-Martin et al., 2012; Ali & Rehman, 2015), the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) also emphasize the importance of an efficient health care system. Improving human health and providing access to inexpensive and high-quality health care are priorities for all countries. Not only is it morally and socially vital, but it is also essential to the long-term sustainability of our economy. Good health enhances

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people's well-being and improves human capital, as healthy students learn better and become more productive workers. Therefore, given the importance of better health care, our study examines how FISD affects the effectiveness of Punjab, Pakistan's health sector, in delivering public services.

Developing countries like Pakistan strive to allocate scarce resources efficiently to improve the effective delivery of basic public services. The state's low tax revenues and high social spending expenditures make its role in setting targets more important in the right direction. The proponents of FISD argue that FISD typically results in more efficient and welfare-enhancing delivery of social services. It is assumed that when resources are pooled at a lower level, local representatives, who are usually more aware of local needs, are held financially accountable, thereby maximizing the effectiveness of local resource allocation (Martinez-Vazquez, 2001; Oates, 1968; Salmon, 1987). Research conducted in high-, low-, and middle-income nations on the effects of FD on health status indicates that the policy is linked to a decrease in the infant mortality rate; however, the precise magnitude of the impact varies depending on the country settings and research designs (Akpan, 2011; Asfaw et al., 2007; Cavalieri & Ferrante, 2016; Jiménez-Rubio, 2011; Ali et al., 2025). However, contrary to the concept of economies of scale, decentralization often fails to fulfil public needs (Litvak et al., 1998). The opponents of FISD also believe that it often increases social and regional disparities due to inefficient social service provision and causes corruption and overspending (Blair, 2000; Kornai et al, 2003; Samoff, 1990; Mehmood et al., 2022). This ambiguity in the narrative asks for further research on how the public service delivery is affected by FISDs.

Health is the inevitable requirement for human development and well-being and is thus considered the foundation of economic development. The health sector is also taken as a metaphor for national prosperity and economic development (Ali, 2015; Xu & Lin, 2022; Audi, 2022). By accelerating growth, enhancing human capital, and reducing poverty and income inequality, investments in the health and education sectors often address a wide range of socioeconomic issues (Barro, 1991; Bhatti & Ahmad,

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2022; Marc & Ali, 2023; Chu et al., 1995; Romer, 1986). After the outbreak of COVID-19, the importance of the public health sector increased, as evidence suggests that countries with high levels of decentralization adopted less stringent policies than those with high levels of centralization (Raja & Iqbal, 2019; Ji et al., 2020; Rocco et al., 2021) during the pandemic. Thus, the impact of FISC on the health sector has received much criticism as many complications, such as diseconomies of scale, no stringent accountability, and inadequate administrative capacities, tend to restrain the local/provisional governments from providing costly medical treatments and immunization (Prud'homme, 1995; Fiszbein, 1997; Litvak et al, 1998). Nevertheless, many past studies have shown that, in many countries, a less unified health sector has proven more efficient and better at catering to local needs (Kaufmann et al., 2005; Anees & Yan, 2019; Robalino et al., 2001; Schwartz, 2002). However, the recent trends toward centralization in many countries again make it worth examining whether decentralization works for Pakistan's health sector.

Pakistan has undergone two major developments in the FISC process. First was the 7th National Financial Commission (NFC) Award in 2010, in which Pakistan dissolved its 17 federal ministries and devolved the financial, legislative, and operational responsibilities to the four provinces. The health ministry was also abolished at the federal level and was given entirely to the provincial domain (Ahmad & Lodhi, 2013; Rehman & Malik, 2020; Russo, 2022). Second was the 18th Amendment to the Constitution, which changed the entire structure of governance and led to a more equitable distribution of financial resources and locally responsible solutions for social sectors, particularly (Mehr et al., 2018). Similarly, the functions of health planning, service regulation, human resource development, legislation, and service delivery programming were also decentralized to the provinces (Zaidi et al., 2019; Khan, 2020). As Pakistan is a federation in which the health sector has undergone devolution, it is plausible to assess the successes and failures of this policy. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the impact of FISC on EPSC in the Health sector of the province of Punjab, Pakistan, from the year 1989 to 2024.

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2. Literature Review

In terms of theory, discussions on FISCAL FEDERALISM (FISD) have been supported by the first- and second-generation theories of fiscal federalism. The first-generation theory aims to link resource allocation more closely with societal requirements, thereby relating FISD to the degree of citizen responsiveness and economic efficiency (Oates, 1972; Tiebout, 1956). The second-generation approach, however, focuses on how providing local governments with incentives and information about individuals may increase economic efficiency (Lockwood, 2002; Wagner, 2007). The past literature on the second-generation theories provides evidence that different sources of revenue have distinct effects on local governments' incentives. Local governments that depend on their own sources of income, such as taxes and fees, are therefore more motivated to provide public goods responsibly, efficiently, and with less corruption (Rodden, 2003; Singh & Srinivasan, 2006) whereas those who depend on federal funds are more likely to be corrupt and have less incentive to increase the effectiveness of local government operations (Brollo et al., 2013; Inanga & Osei-Wusu, 2004; Rahat & Hayat, 2020; Carli, 2025).

A study of the empirical literature on FISD reveals that since the 1980s, a large body of research has been published related to the efficiency of the local governments or the one that links FISD with economic growth. However, there is still a paucity of research examining the connection relationship between FISD and efficiency of public service delivery (EPSD) especially in developing countries (Afonso & Fernandes, 2008; Boetti et al., 2012; Narbón-Perpiñá & De Witte, 2016; Ufaq, 2019; Marc & Roussel, 2024). Moreover, there is also a split in the findings of the existing research, whilst some studies (Modibbo & Inuwa, 2020; Adam, Delis, & Kammas, 2014; Kaufmann, Kraay, & Zoido-Lobaton, 2002) find a positive effect of FISD on EPSD, others (De Mello Jr, 2004; Zhang & Zou, 1998) report a negative one.

Mehr-un-Nisa and Khalil (2018) studied the role of FISD in improving public services across 8 districts of Punjab. The study covers the period 2003 to 2014, and to further analyze the effect of regime change, it decomposes the period into the Pervaiz Musharraf regime

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and the period after the end of the Pervaiz Musharraf regime. The health and education sectors have been selected for analysis of public-sector performance. Primary school enrollment has been used as a proxy for educational output, while the percentage of children aged 12 to 23 months immunized has been used as a proxy for health output. To measure FISD in both sectors, the logs of total district expenditures on health and education and total district expenditures per capita on health and education have been used. The findings show a significant, positive effect of FISD on both health and education outputs. Moreover, the results show that the FISD policy was effective only before 2008 (during Pervaiz Musharraf's regime); after that period, the results reversed. The study favors the enhancement and distribution of power to the lower tiers of society.

Ahmed and Baloch (2019) also analyzed the impact of FISD, specifically after the implementation of 7th NFC award, on the education and health sector of the Baluchistan province. After the 18th amendment, the implementation of 7th NFC award had broader consequences for provinces in both the vertical and horizontal distribution criteria. Amongst others, Baluchistan province was a key beneficiary whose share sharply increased from merely 3.2% to 9.09% besides the release of 120 million rupees from the federal government. Thus, considering this bigger fiscal space and constitutional mandate, performance of Baluchistan in the delivery of social services, including education and health sectors, was expected to improve. Considering this, the study takes into account six districts of Baluchistan for the time period 1985 to 2014. FISD has been measured through the overall expenditures on education and health sectors in Baluchistan. The adult literacy rate has been used to measure educational outcomes whereas infant mortality rate and crude death rate have been taken as measures for health outcomes. The results show a negative effect of FISD on educational outcomes. The performance of the education sector was worsening in Baluchistan despite heavy budget allocation. In case of the health sector, the role of provincial autonomy and FISD was insignificant. The findings suggest that Baluchistan, despite having administrative and fiscal autonomy and better fiscal position, failed to improve the education and health sectors. According to the

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authors, the main reasons behind such inefficiency are corruption and sheer embezzlement of public finances.

Ahmed & Lodhi (2016) empirically analyzed the effect of FISC on the performance of education and health sectors of the provinces of Pakistan over the period 1975 to 2009. The performance of the health sector is measured using infant mortality rate and crude death rate while that of the education sector is measured by combined literacy rate for both males and females. The results show that FISC positively and significantly affects the performance of the health sector when considering overall Pakistan. However, when each province is considered separately, it is found that FISC decreases infant mortality rate only in Punjab and Sindh. On the contrary, FISC has a positive influence on the performance of the education sector for overall Pakistan as well for each of the four provinces. Specifically considering the health sector, Zaidi et al., (2019) have theoretically analyzed the impact of Pakistan's radical, politically motivated provincial devolution on country's ability to modernize its overall health system and enhance health planning and spending. The analysis showed that since the process of this political devolution was very abrupt and the provincial setup was not completely ready for this, there was actually only a partial devolution afterwards. Moreover, in decentralized Pakistan, although health became a priority in the government expenditure, priorities for allocation were not set properly and little effort was done in address inequalities. Provincially contextualized health care planning and legislation was given importance but implementation remained very poor. Expenditures for healthcare system did increase but the performance did not speed up to that level. The study demonstrates that while strong political-bureaucratic ownership of health promoted development, weak national coordination, frequent leadership changes and limited stewardship abilities at the subnational level and interference by local elites restricted successful implementation.

Arends (2017) also analyzed the impact of FISC on the health care sector using the cross-country data set for 25 OECD countries for the time period 1995 to 2013. The author first examined the effect of FISC on expenditure allocated to the public healthcare sector,

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and then examined the effect of decentralization on the effectiveness and efficiency of the healthcare sector. The findings show that decentralizing spending leads to a larger public health sector, but it is those with poor health outcomes who benefit. However, decentralizing tax authority has no effect on the size of the health sector and may even improve its performance.

Rubio (2010) also examined the impact of FISD on the health sector of 19 (less developed and developed) OECD countries. This study contributes to the previous literature by using an improved measure for FISD developed by Stegarescu in 2005. This indicator measures FISD as ratio of local government's tax revenue share to the overall share of government in the tax revenue. For the purpose of comparison, the study also includes the conventional measure of FISD (share of local government's expenditure to government's total expenditure). Infant mortality is used to measure the health outcomes. The findings illustrate a significant and negative relationship between FISD and infant mortality. The expenditure-based approach overestimates the results while the tax revenue-based approach gave the benchmark results. The findings illustrate that 1 % increase in local government's share in tax revenue leads to 0.05% reduction in infant mortality while a 1% increase in the share of local government's expenditure leads to 0.2% decrease in infant mortality. Similar positive effect of FISD on the efficiency of the health sector of Pakistan was also reported by Faridi et al. (2020).

Unlike the previous studies that considered infant mortality rate as an indicator for health outcomes, Rotulo et al, (2021) analyzed the effect of FISD on the availability, accessibility and usage of healthcare services in 19 regions and 2 autonomous provinces (Trento and Bolzano) of Italy over the period 2001 to 2017. The Italian national health system introduced a strong FISD element in 2001 which made regions responsible for their own pooling of resources and of their budgets thus, made them equally autonomous. The ratio of local region's health expenditure to total public health expenditure is used to measure FISD. The availability of health services is measured in terms of the density of human (density of general practitioners per 10,000 population and density

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of public and private healthcare staff divided by total staff, doctors and nurses at primary, secondary and tertiary level of care) and technical resources (density of total public and private hospital beds available and density of medical machinery available per 10,000 population at primary, secondary and tertiary level of healthcare). To measure the accessibility of health care the study uses the percentage of hospitalized patients residing in the same region where hospitalization event occurred. This was done to estimate the potential geographic barriers to access. To quantify the utilization of healthcare the study uses the total and acute hospitalization rates in public and private hospitals, that is number of cared patients leaving or discharged from the hospital after spending at least one night.

The results show that FIRD leads to a decrease in the availability of health care staff and hospital beds, a decrease in the utilization of health services, and an increase in interregional disparities due to increased patient mobilization to access healthcare. The effect was greater in public than in private healthcare services, and in already poor, austerity-based regions. The results show that Italy's health care system did not perform well after decentralization, as evidenced by its collapse during the COVID-19 emergency.

3. Model Specification and Data Sources

The effect of FIRD on EPSD in the health sector of Pakistan is determined through a two-step estimation procedure. In step I, efficiency coefficients are estimated through stochastic frontier technique. Model I is used for this purpose:

$$INFM_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 EOH_t + \alpha_2 GDPC_t + \alpha_3 POP_t + \alpha_4 PDENSITY_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (I)$$

where INFM is the infant mortality rate (number of infants (age less than 1 year) dying per 1000 live births in a given year), EOH is the public expenditure on health as percentage of GDP, GDPC is GDP per capita, POP is the annual growth rate of population and PDENSITY is the population density per square kilometer.

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In step II, the effect of FISD on efficiency coefficients is determined using Model II

$$ECINFM_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FISD_t + \beta_2 GNP_t + \beta_3 INFL_t + \beta_4 UE_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (II)$$

where ECINFM represents the efficiency coefficients estimated in step I and FISD is fiscal decentralization. FISD is not directly measurable so two proxies, namely revenue decentralization (RED) and expenditure decentralization (EXD) are used to measure FISD.

$$RED = \frac{PREV}{PREV + FREV}$$

Where PREV is provincial revenue and FREV is federal revenue.

$$EXD = \frac{PEXP}{PEXP + FEXP}$$

Where PEXP is provincial expenditure and FEXP is federal expenditure.

Other control variables are Gross Nation Product (GNP), inflation (INLF), measured using Consumer Price Index (CPI) and unemployment rate (UE).

The data for infant mortality rate is taken from World Development Indicators (WDI) and that of other independent variables is taken from various issues of the Economic Survey of Pakistan.

3.1. Econometric Methodology

To estimate the effect of Fiscal Intergovernmental System Design (FISD) on Efficiency of Public Sector Delivery (EPSD) in Pakistan's health sector, a two-step estimation procedure has been adopted. In the first step, the Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) technique is used to estimate the efficiency coefficients of Model I. SFA, which is a method introduced by Aigner et al. (1977) and Meeusen and Van den Broeck (1977), estimates how efficiently some economic entities perform activities by comparing observed outputs to the maximum possible output, given a set of inputs. SFA is a parametric method (Sarwar et al., 2022) because it uses specific

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assumptions about the relationship between inputs and outputs and accounts for random error. In the second step, regression analysis is used to estimate the effect of FIRD on the efficiency coefficients.

It's crucial to verify the integration order of the variables, as the analysis uses time-series data. For this, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is used.

The short- and long-run relationships among the study's variables are estimated using the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound testing approach, a statistical method designed to test for relationships between variables in both the short- and long-run. The F-test, a statistical test that assesses whether group means differ, is used to determine whether a long-run relationship exists between the variables of interest (Iqbal et al., 2023). Once it is established that a long-run relationship exists, the maximum lag length—that is, the number of past time periods included in the model—used to obtain the long-run results is calculated using Schwartz Bayesian Criteria (SBC), a method for selecting the model with the best fit. Having done this, various post-estimation tests are applied to check the robustness and reliability of the results.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Stochastic Frontier Analysis Results for Efficiency Coefficients of Infant Mortality Rate

Model I is estimated using SFA to determine the efficiency coefficients for infant mortality rate. The results are represented in Table 1.

Table 1: *Efficiency Coefficients of INFM*

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	Probability
Constant	0.184	0.10004	0.001
EOH	- 0.146	0.03710	0.032
GDPC	-0.655	0.12084	0.004

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POP	-0.481	0.01852	0.054
PDENSITY	0.267	0.10000	0.074

Log likelihood: -0.17
LR test: 0.75

The results show that EOH and GDPC have a significant and negative effect on INFM. A 1% increase in EOH causes a 14.6% decrease in INFM, whereas a 1% increase in GDPC leads to a 65.5% decrease in INFM. Increased expenditure on health ensures the availability of better health care facilities, which, in turn, reduces mortality rates (Abbasi & Sohail, 2022; Dhrifi, 2019; Owusu et al., 2021). Moreover, higher GDP per capita indicates better living standards, which means people can better afford health care facilities and reduce mortality rates (Upadhyay & Srivastava, 2012). The association of POP and PDENSITY with INFM is found to be insignificant. These results are consistent with those of Sow et al. (2015). The model is a good fit because the LR test statistic (0.75) is greater than the log-likelihood value (- 0.17).

The yearly efficiency coefficient of INFM from 1989 to 2024 is calculated and reported in Table 2.

Table 2: *Yearly Efficiency Estimates of INFM*

Years	Efficiency Coefficients	Years	Efficiency Coefficients
1989	0.77	2007	0.59
1990	0.77	2008	0.60
1991	0.74	2009	0.58
1992	0.74	2010	0.56
1993	0.72	2011	0.58

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1994	0.70	2012	0.60
1995	0.69	2013	0.61
1996	0.70	2014	0.68
1997	0.69	2015	0.71
1998	0.67	2016	0.76
1999	0.67	2017	0.72
2000	0.67	2018	0.73
2001	0.66	2019	0.87
2002	0.65	2020	0.87
2003	0.66	2021	0.86
2004	0.65	2022	0.88
2005	0.62	2023	0.99
2006	0.61	2024	0.98

Mean Efficiency = 0.7076

The results show that the mean health efficiency over the period 1989-2024 is approximately 71%, suggesting an approximate 29% increase in health efficiency is possible. These improvements can be achieved by more efficient use of public expenditure and other resources in the health sector.

4.2. Impact of Fiscal Decentralization On Efficiency of Public Service Delivery in Health Sector

To estimate the effect of Fisd on ECINFM, firstly the stationarity of the variables is checked using ADF test.

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Table 3: ADF Test Results

Variables	Level	First Difference	Results
GNP	4.10		I (0)
RED	-16.57		I (0)
EXD	-2.96	-8.13	I (1)
UE	-1.96	-5.91	I (1)
INFL	-2.71	-7.44	I (1)
ECINFM	0.63	-4.94	I (1)

The results of the ADF test show that GNP and RED are stationary at the level, while EXD, UE, INFL, and ECINFM are stationary at the first difference. Since the variables have a mixed order of integration and none of the variables is stationary at the second difference, the prerequisites for applying the ARDL model have been fulfilled (Pesaran, Shin, & Smith, 2001).

After checking the variable integration order, an optimal lag length of 2 is selected using SBC. Thereafter, it is checked whether a long-run relationship exists between the study's key variables.

Table 4: Bound Test Results

F-statistics value	95% Confidence Level		90% Confidence Level	
	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
14.49	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52

The results of the Bound test indicate that the F-statistic (14.49) exceeds the Upper Bound at both the 90% and 95% confidence levels; hence, we confirm that a long-run relationship exists between the variables under consideration.

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Once we have confirmed the existence of a long-run relationship between the study's variables, the short- and long-run effects of FISD on EPSD in the health sector are reported in Tables 5 and 6, respectively.

Table 5: *Short Run Estimates, ARDL (1 1 2 1 1 1)*

Dependent Variable: ECINFM

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	probability
ECINFM (-1)	0.80	0.12421	0.000
RED	0.182	0.10210	0.039
RED (-1)	0.203	0.13421	0.001
EXD	-0.166	0.03974	0.049
EXD (-1)	-0.11	0.02841	0.035
EXD (-2)	-0.213	0.02134	0.032
GNP	0.11	0.04866	0.000
GNP (-1)	0.155	0.04620	0.001
UE	-0.03	0.01835	0.833
UE (-1)	-0.011	0.01648	0.012
INFL	-0.048	0.05334	0.433
INFL (-1)	-0.143	0.05170	0.446
Constant	0.077	0.05831	0.042
ECT	-0.66	0.53	0.002

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$R^2 = 0.976$

Adjusted $R^2 = 0.975$

The short-run results show that FISC, measured through RED and EXD, significantly affects the efficiency of the health sector. However, RED positively affects health efficiency, while the effect of EXD is negative. A 1% increase in RED leads to an 18.2% increase in the ECINFM, while a similar increase in EXD causes a 16.6% decrease in ECINFM. These results are similar to those reported by Ambreen et al. (2022), Chen et al. (2023), and Sow, Razafimahefa, and Akitoby (2015). For the case of EXD, the results match the findings of Sow, Razafimahefa, and Akitoby (2015), who pointed out that the effect of fiscal decentralization on health outcomes was not mediated by the government's health spending. The negative impact of expenditure decentralization stems from the challenges and obstacles encountered in operationalizing FISC and public service delivery in developing countries like Pakistan. The sub-national government's lack of accountability and corruption can lead to inefficient outcomes. Sow et al. (2015) suggested that a lack of management and corruption in the EXD process can reduce EPSD. In this context, Ahmed and Lodhi (2016) emphasized that while FISC can promote corruption, good governance is necessary to attain effective outcomes in the health sector. Moreover, Sow et al. (2015) noted that the average level of expenditure decentralization is only about 25% in developing countries. However, this level needs to exceed 35.7% for the health sector to improve the efficiency of public services.

The effect of GNP on the efficiency of the health sector is also positive and significant. The results show that a 1% increase in GNP leads to an 11% improvement in the ECINFM. However, the effect of both UE and INFL on the efficiency of the health sector is insignificant. The R^2 and Adjusted R^2 values indicate that the model is a good fit.

The results also show that the coefficient of the Error Correction Model (ECM) term (ECT) is negative and significant, indicating that the system tends to revert to its long-run equilibrium. A roughly 66% correction is made in each time period.

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Table 6: Long Run Estimates, ARDL (1 1 2 1 1 1)

Dependent Variable: ECINFM

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Errors	Probability
RED	0.1860	0.20143	0.000
EXD	0.1162	0.03420	0.032
GNP	0.1325	0.10423	0.003
UE	-0.1630	0.6040	0.042
INFL	-0.1216	0.05178	0.719

The log-run results (reported in Table 6) show that both measures of fiscal decentralization (RED and EXD) positively and significantly affect ECINFM. A 1% increase in RED and EXD results in 18.6% and 11.6% improvements in the health sector's efficiency, respectively. These results match those presented by Rubio (2010) and Sow et al. (2015). Similarly, GNP also positively and significantly affects the efficiency of the health sector. A 1% increase in GNP contributes 13.25% increase in the efficiency of the health sector. A higher GNP indicates a better standard of living; people have more to spend on health facilities, and hence the infant mortality rate decreases. The unemployment rate negatively affects the efficiency of the health sector. A 1% increase in the unemployment rate leads to a 16.3% decrease in ECINFM. The effect of inflation on the efficiency of the health sector is insignificant.

4.3. Diagnostic Test Results

Various diagnostic tests are applied to check the stability of the model and the results. The results are presented in Table 7 below:

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Table 7: *Results of Diagnostic Tests*

Tests	Probability	Conclusion
Ramsey RESET Test	0.214	Model is correctly specified.
Lagrange Multiplier Test	0.263	Residuals are free from serial correlation.
White Test	0.457	No hetroskedasticity found

Since probability values are greater than 0.05 in diagnostic tests, it is concluded that the model is correctly specified and the residuals are not serially correlated and are homoscedastic. This confirms the validity of the fitted model and implies that the estimated parameters of the model are accurate and can offer helpful insights for the implication of economic policy.

Finally, the stability of the model is checked using CUSUM and CUSUM square tests. Since both the plots (Shown in Fig 1 and Fig 2) do not cross the critical value lines, it is concluded that the estimated parameters are stable and can safely be used for policy purposes.

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Fig 1: Plot of CUSUM

Fig 2: Plot of CUSUMSQ

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5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

The study investigates the role that FSD can play in improving the efficiency of the health sector of Punjab, Pakistan. The results reveal that in the short run, only RED positively and significantly contributes towards enhancing the efficiency of the health sector. However, ultimately in the long run, both RED and EXD have a positive influence on the efficiency of the health sector of Punjab, Pakistan. Based on the study's results, it is suggested that subnational governments broaden their tax base to raise more revenue. The increased tax revenue will further enhance long-term efficiency in Pakistan's health sector. Motivating people to pay taxes and taking action against tax defaulters should be a priority. Moreover, in order to benefit from EXD, EXD should be allowed to exceed a certain level (as suggested by Sow et al. (2015)). Also, to prevent the misappropriation of public funds, there should be strict anti-corruption regulations and increased institutional accountability.

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